

Carbon Stability and Screening-Level Soil Chemical Responses of Waste-Derived Biochars Under Short-Term Dry Incubation

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Article History:

Received: 07.01.2026 Revised: 05.02.2026 Accepted: 06.02.2026 Published: 11.02.2026

ABSTRACT:

Converting heterogeneous waste streams into stable carbon materials while minimizing environmental risk is an important goal in sustainable waste management. In this study, waste-derived biochars produced at 500 °C from municipal solid waste (MSW), end-of-life rubber tires (RT), and wood waste (WW) were evaluated for long-term carbon stability and short-term soil chemical responses. Carbon stability was assessed using elemental ratios, fixed carbon content, carbon yield, and carbon sequestration efficiency. Biochars derived from MSW and RT showed low H/C and O/C ratios, high fixed carbon contents, and retained approximately one-third of their original feedstock carbon, indicating strong potential for long-term persistence in soil environments. Short-term soil chemical responses were characterized using a controlled soil incubation. Changes in soil chemistry were primarily associated with limited ash dissolution rather than nutrient enrichment. Electrical conductivity increased moderately but remained below salinity thresholds, and exchangeable calcium (Ca) increased consistently across treatments. Soil pH declined slightly in soils amended with MSW and RT biochars, while WW biochar caused minimal change. Micronutrient behavior varied by feedstock. Copper (Cu) and manganese (Mn) generally declined, suggesting immobilization on biochar surfaces, whereas zinc (Zn) decreased in soils amended with MSW and WW biochars but increased with RT biochar due to its inherent Zn content. Trace metal concentrations in all biochars were below international guideline values, although their long-term mobility under field-relevant dynamic conditions remains uncertain. Overall, the results indicate that waste-derived biochars provide chemically stable carbon inputs to soils, with short-term soil chemical responses serving as indicators of environmental compatibility.

Keywords: Waste-derived biochar; Carbon stability; Soil chemical response; Pyrolysis; Trace metals.

Suggested Citation: E. Arzadon, E.J. Baticados, S. Capareda, "Carbon Stability and Screening-Level Soil Chemical Responses of Waste-Derived Biochars Under Short-Term Dry Incubation," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 4(1), pp. 178-193, Jan-Feb 2026. DOI: 10.59324/ejaset.2026.4(1).11

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INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand for sustainable waste management has intensified interest in thermochemical conversion technologies that recover value from diverse waste streams [1, 2]. Among these, pyrolysis has gained prominence for its ability to transform organic and waste feedstocks into energy-rich products and stable carbon materials [3]. Biochar, the carbonaceous solid co-product of pyrolysis, has gained increasing attention for its capacity to sequester carbon, improve soil fertility, and immobilize contaminants [4], while also supporting global climate mitigation efforts by stabilizing organic carbon over long timescales and advancing circular economy pathways through the valorization of agricultural and municipal residues. To ensure environmental quality and carbon accounting integrity, biochar production and application are increasingly guided by recognized standards such as the International Biochar Initiative (IBI) and the European Biochar Certificate (EBC), which set specifications for feedstock quality, metal thresholds, and intended land applications.

The properties and environmental performance of biochar depend primarily on feedstock composition and pyrolysis conditions [5-7]. Among the operational variables, temperature is the most decisive factor controlling the extent of carbonization, volatile removal, and aromatic condensation. Higher temperatures (400-900 °C) typically enhance carbon stability and fixed carbon yield while lowering overall mass recovery [5]. Around 500°C, however, pyrolysis produces biochar that balance between carbon stability with surface reactivity [4, 8, 9]. For these reasons, a temperature of 500 °C was selected for this study.

Although many studies document improvements in soil aggregation, water-holding capacity, and nutrient dynamics [10-12], the literature remains dominated by lignocellulosic feedstocks such as wood, crop residues, and paper fiber [13-15]. Expanding pyrolysis inputs to municipal solid waste (MSW) and end-of-life rubber tires (RT) offers an opportunity to convert challenging waste streams into carbon-stable materials that can support resource recovery and landfill diversion. Yet these unconventional feedstocks may contain elevated concentrations of metals such as Pb, Cd, As, Cr, and Ni [16], which could pose agronomic or ecological risks if land-applied without proper characterization. This underscores the need for screening-level studies that evaluate the chemical properties, stability indices, and potential metal burdens of waste-derived biochars prior to field-scale use.

Initial soil incubation experiments provide a controlled means to assess early-phase biochar–soil interactions [17, 18]. Short-term trials - particularly under relatively dry conditions capture conservative estimates of pH shifts, EC, ion dissolution, nutrient availability, and trace mobility before moisture-driven transformations dominate. The use of a 10% application rate, though higher than typical field rates, is a recognized approach for mechanistic differentiation among contrasting biochars [19] and allows clearer detection of short-term chemical responses. Likewise, a 45-day incubation focuses intentionally on the rapid, initial reactions that define early soil conditioning effects and inform subsequent, field-realistic experimentation [20].

In this context, the objective of this study was to evaluate waste-derived biochars produced from MSW, RT, and WW with respect to their long-term carbon stability and short-term soil chemical responses. Specifically, the study aimed to:

- a. quantify pyrolysis product distributions to assess carbon retention across different waste feedstocks;
- b. characterize the physicochemical and elemental properties of the resulting biochars, with emphasis on carbon stability indicators and trace metal concentrations; and
- c. examine early abiotic soil chemical responses, including changes in pH, EC, and nutrient and trace metal behavior, using a short-term soil incubation as a screening-level assessment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Pyrolysis Conditions and Characterization

Feedstocks were sourced from the eAI Institute (Magnolia, TX, USA). The WW and MSW were supplied in pelletized form, with the MSW preprocessed to remove glass, metals, and other bulk inorganics. The RT was provided in powdered form with steel components removed prior to use.

Pyrolysis experiments were conducted using a batch-type high-pressure/high-temperature reactor (Series 4570 HP/HT, Parr Instrument Company) located in the Bio Energy Testing and Analysis (BETA) Laboratory at Texas A&M University. A schematic of the reactor setup is shown in Figure 1. Approximately 500 g of each feedstock was loaded into the reactor vessel, which was then sealed to maintain an inert atmosphere. The system was purged with nitrogen gas (N₂) for 15 minutes to remove residual oxygen before heating. The reactor was heated to 500 °C and held for approximately five hours, or until gas flow became negligible. After the reaction, the system was allowed to cool naturally to room temperature. Product yields of bio-oil, syngas, and solid biochar were quantified gravimetrically. The resulting biochar was collected and stored in airtight containers for subsequent physicochemical characterization.

Proximate and ultimate analyses were performed to establish the initial compositional and elemental characteristics of the three feedstocks. These baseline parameters were used to evaluate carbon redistribution across pyrolysis products and the initial carbon content of the biochar relevant to its carbon sequestration potential and long-term stability in soil. Proximate analysis (moisture, volatile matter, ash, and fixed carbon by difference) followed the ASTM D3172 [21]. Ultimate analysis was conducted using a vario Micro Cube Analyzer (Elementar Americas Inc., NY, USA) to determine carbon (C), hydrogen (H), nitrogen (N), and sulfur (S) contents, with oxygen calculated by difference.

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of the Laboratory Scale Pyrolysis Reactor used for Biochar Production at 500°C

Determination of Biochar Stability and Carbon Storage Potential

Ultimate analysis provided the basis for calculating hydrogen-to-carbon and oxygen-to-carbon molar ratios, which served as indicators of aromatic condensation and oxidation state [22]. These ratios were computed from elemental mass fractions as:

$$H/Corg = (Hw/1.008) \div (Cw/12.01) \quad (1a)$$

$$O/Corg = (Ow/16.00) \div (Cw/12.01) \quad (1b)$$

Lower *H/Corg* ratios were interpreted as evidence of increased aromaticity and greater thermal recalcitrance, while *O/Corg* ratios were used to assess the degree of surface oxidation and corresponding susceptibility to microbial degradation. These values were later used to classify the chars into stability tiers based on published thresholds (e.g., *H/Corg* ≤ 0.4 indicating highly stable, long-lived carbon).

Carbon stability was further classified using published *H/Corg* and *O/Corg* thresholds: *O/Corg* < 0.2 indicates biochar half-lives >1000 years, 0.2–0.6 indicates 100–1000 years, and >0.6 reflects half-lives <100 years. Volatile matter (VM) content was also used as a complementary stability index; VM > 80% (ash-free) denotes low stability, whereas VM < 80% in combination with *H/Corg* < 0.4 or *O/Corg* < 0.2 indicates high carbon sequestration potential [23].

Biochar carbon yield, defined as the fraction of original feedstock carbon retained in the solid phase, was estimated by combining the gravimetric yield of biochar with its carbon mass fraction. For a given dry feedstock mass, the percentage of carbon retained was calculated as:

$$C\text{-yield (\%)} = (Ybc \times Cbc/Cf) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where *Ybc* is the dry biochar yield (kg biochar/kg feedstock), *Cbc* is the carbon mass fraction of the biochar, and *Cf* is the carbon mass fraction of the feedstock. These values provided a direct measure of pyrolysis carbon-retention efficiency at 500 °C.

Long-term carbon storage potential was further assessed by combining carbon yield with stability-based permanence factors (*Fperm*). Corresponding *Fperm* were applied based on *H/Corg* with 0.74 assigned for *H/Corg* < 0.4 and 0.56 for *H/Corg* > 0.4 [23, 24]. Carbon sequestration efficiency (CSE) was then calculated as:

$$CSE (\%) = C\text{-yield (\%)} \times Fperm \quad (3)$$

representing the proportion of feedstock carbon expected to remain stored in soil over centennial timescales.

Soil-Biochar Incubation

This incubation experiment was designed as a screening-level experiment to isolate early abiotic soil-biochar interactions rather than to simulate field application conditions similar to the study conducted by Brassard et al. [25]. Biochar samples were first manually pre-pulverized using a mortar and pestle to break down large aggregates and facilitate consistent milling. The pre-crushed material was then processed using a Wiley Mill (Thomas Scientific, NJ, USA), which provided uniform mechanical grinding. Following milling, the ground biochar was passed through a Tyler No. 9 sieve (<2 mm), and only those smaller than 2 mm were retained to ensure particle size uniformity and improved comparability across treatments.

Each biochar type was mixed with a commercial topsoil at a 10% rate (dry mass basis), which exceeds typical field application rates but is commonly employed in screening-level incubation studies to enable mechanistic differentiation among contrasting biochars and to enhance the detection of short-term abiotic soil chemical responses [19]. For each treatment, the appropriate mass of biochar was thoroughly homogenized with nine parts soil using a stainless-steel mixing tray, and the mixtures were apportioned into polyethylene pots in triplicate. Control pots containing only

soil were prepared in the same manner. The mixtures were maintained at their ambient moisture content, and no additional water was added during the incubation period to suppress microbial activity and limit ash dissolution and to focus on early dilution, ion exchange, and surface sorption processes. All pots were kept under laboratory conditions at approximately 25 °C to 27 °C for 45 days, similarly to another biochar study by [20]. The containers were loosely covered to limit dust contamination while allowing gas exchange, and no plants were grown during this period. At the end of incubation, subsamples from each pot were collected and submitted for routine soil analysis, including pH, EC, macronutrients, micronutrients, and trace metals to quantify the changes in soil chemistry induced by the 10% biochar additions.

Physicochemical Characterization

Soil samples were collected and analyzed using standard laboratory procedures in collaboration with the Texas A&M University Soil, Water, and Forage Testing Laboratory (SWFL). Soil pH and EC were measured in a 1:20 soil to water slurry using a calibrated bench top pH meter and conductivity meter (Metler Toledo, OH, USA).

Nitrate nitrogen (NO₃-N), dry-basis, was extracted with 1N KCl solution and quantified spectrophotometrically following cadmium reduction to nitrite. Selected macronutrients including phosphorus (P), potassium (K), calcium (Ca), and sulfur (S) are extracted using the Mehlich III extractant. The extractant is a dilute acid-fluoride-EDTA solution of pH 2.5 that consists of 0.2 N CH₃-COOH-0.25 N NH₄NO₃-0.015 N NH₄F-0.013 N HNO₃-0.001 M EDTA. The micronutrients including copper (Cu), manganese (Mn) and zinc (Zn) are extracted using a 0.005 M DTPA, 0.01 M CaCl₂ and 0.10 M triethanolamine solution. All the analytes were analyzed by inductively coupled plasma (Perkin Elmer, CT, USA) spectrometry for precise multi-element quantification.

Trace Metal Characterization

Selected trace heavy metals including arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), lead (Pb), and nickel (Ni) were measured to investigate potential soil contamination or mobilization following biochar application based on the IBI's digestion and determination method for toxicants assessment and US EPA 7000 [24].

Statistical Analysis

All measurements were conducted in triplicate for each treatment. Results were reported as the mean with the associated standard deviation to represent within treatment variability. Treatment effects on soil chemical properties were evaluated using one-way fixed-effects ANOVA. When ANOVA indicated significant differences ($p < 0.05$), pairwise comparisons were assessed using Tukey's HSD test, and treatment means were grouped accordingly. All data analyses were conducted using JMP[®]16 (SAS Institute, NC, USA).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Product Distribution and Routine Compositional Analysis of Biochars

The distribution of pyrolysis products at 500 °C highlights how feedstock composition governs carbon conversion pathways and product selectivity (Figure 2). Among the three feedstocks, RT produced the highest biochar yield at 52.71%, followed by MSW at 28.13% and WW at 26.35%. The elevated solid yield from rubber corresponds with its high fixed carbon content and low volatile fraction, which favor char retention and thermal stability. In contrast, MSW and WW, both rich in oxygenated and volatile components, generated greater proportions of condensable and gaseous products.

Bio-oil production was highest for WW at 38.49%, indicating efficient devolatilization and condensation of lignocellulosic vapors into liquid fractions. MSW produced a comparable but slightly lower bio-oil yield (31.55%), while RT generated only 29.21%, consistent with its higher aromaticity and tendency toward gas evolution rather than tar formation. Syngas yield was greatest in MSW at 40.32%, followed by WW at 35.16% and RT at 18.08%.

Figure 2. Pyrolysis Product Yield (%) Distributions and Raw Biochar Morphology for WW, MSW, and RT at 500 °C, Shown Prior to Any Milling or Sieving Steps

Table 1. Proximate, Ultimate, and Bulk Density Characteristics of MSW, RT, and WW Biochars

Properties	MSW	RT	WW
Proximate Analysis			
MC, %	1.47 ± 0.10	1.83 ± 0.12	3.95 ± 0.21
VCM, %	17.79 ± 0.72	7.78 ± 0.31	16.79 ± 0.65
Ash, %	8.47 ± 0.34	12.42 ± 0.50	14.61 ± 0.58
FC, %	72.27 ± 1.21	77.97 ± 0.97	64.65 ± 1.05
Bulk Density			
kg m ³	299.25 ± 20.10	1270.00 ± 45.00	620.00 ± 28.50
lb ft ³	18.68 ± 1.25	79.28 ± 2.81	38.71 ± 1.78
Ultimate Analysis			
C, %	87.60 ± 1.45	85.02 ± 1.70	75.70 ± 1.52
H, %	2.93 ± 0.10	2.33 ± 0.08	3.70 ± 0.12
O, %	4.91 ± 0.28	9.21 ± 0.40	20.30 ± 0.90
N, %	4.45 ± 0.18	0.94 ± 0.05	0.20 ± 0.02
S, %	0.11 ± 0.01	2.50 ± 0.09	0.10 ± 0.01

Volatile matter was lowest in RT and highest in MSW and WW (Table 1), consistent with the greater presence of thermally reactive organic fractions in lignocellulosic and mixed waste feedstocks [26]. Fixed carbon was highest in RT, suggesting a tendency to form more carbon rich and thermally stable char, while WW contained the highest ash content, which may introduce more mineral phases capable of influencing soil chemical conditions. Ultimate analysis further emphasized these differences. MSW and RT had the highest carbon contents, while WW contained more oxygen, typical of lignocellulosic biomass. The gradual decrease in oxygen to carbon ratio from WW to RT to MSW indicates a shift toward increased aromaticity, which may contribute to slower degradation once added to soil. Nitrogen was greatest in MSW, indicating possible nutrient contributions, while RT contained more sulfur, which may require attention depending on the soil environment.

Biochar Stability and Carbon Storage Potential

The MSW and RT chars had high carbon contents (87.60% and 85.02%) and low oxygen contents (4.91% and 9.21%), giving low atomic ratios (using Eq. 1) of H/C_{org} (0.40 and 0.33) and O/C_{org} (0.04 and 0.08). In contrast, WW char retained more oxygen (20.30%), yielding $H/C_{org} = 0.58$ and $O/C_{org} = 0.20$. On the Van Krevelen diagram (Figure 3), MSW and RT cluster at the low H/C –low O/C end of the typical biomass carbonization trajectory, while WW plots at a more oxidized position. These values fall within published stability classes where $H/C_{org} \leq 0.4$ and $O/C_{org} < 0.2$ are

associated with highly aromatic carbon and modeled half-lives approaching or exceeding 100-1000 years [22-24]. WW, with $H/C_{org} > 0.4$ and O/C_{org} at the 0.2 boundary, is therefore assigned to a moderate stability tier.

Proximate analysis supports this pattern. Fixed carbon contents were highest in RT (77.97%) and MSW (72.27%) and lowest in PW (64.65%), while volatile matter remained well below the 80% (ash-free) threshold used to flag unstable materials [23]. The combination of low H/C_{org} , very low O/C_{org} , and high fixed carbon in RT and MSW chars is consistent with extensive devolatilization and the formation of condensed polyaromatic domains [7], whereas WW retains a larger fraction of partially oxidized or labile structures [27].

Carbon yields integrate this chemical recalcitrance with the efficiency of carbon retention during pyrolysis. Using Equation 2, the RT and MSW chars retained 53.3% and 51.6% of their initial feedstock carbon, respectively, while WW retained 39.7%, reflecting greater volatilization of lignocellulosic carbon into vapors and permanent gases, as commonly observed for woody feedstocks at similar temperatures [6]. Applying stability-based permanence factors derived from H/C_{org} ($F_{perm} = 0.74$ for MSW and RT; 0.56 for WW; [23]) yields carbon sequestration efficiencies of about 38% for MSW, 39% for RT, and 22% for PW. Thus, MSW and RT biochars are expected to store almost twice as much feedstock carbon over centennial timescales as WW biochar.

Figure 3. Van Krevelen Diagram Showing the Atomic H/C and O/C of MSW, RT, and WW Biochars Produced at 500°C, Indicating Increased Aromaticity and Stability Relative to Typical Biomass Carbonization Pathways

Taken together, the molar ratios, fixed carbon contents, carbon yields, and CSE values converge on the same ranking of long-term sequestration potential: $RT \approx MSW \gg PW$. RT performs slightly better than MSW because of its very high fixed carbon and strong carbon retention, but both qualify as highly stable biochars under current stability criteria. PW still contributes to carbon storage but exhibits lower aromatic condensation and lower retention efficiency. These results show that unconventional feedstocks such as municipal solid waste and end-of-life tires can yield exceptionally stable, carbon-rich biochars that rival or surpass wood-derived materials in their capacity for durable carbon sequestration.

Early-Phase Soil Responses to Biochar Application

Soil pH and Electrical Conductivity

Contrary to the widely reported liming effect of biochar [28], both the MSW and RT chars induced a slight acidification of the soil, decreasing pH from 7.10 in the control to 6.80 and 6.60, respectively (Figure 4a). Similar acidifying effects have been reported for biochars with oxygenated acidic functional groups or partially oxidized organic residues that release weak acids, including phenolic and carboxylic groups, during early dissolution in neutral soils [29]. RT biochar, in particular, is known to preserve sulfonated and oxygen-rich aromatic structures after pyrolysis [30], likely explaining the stronger decline in soil pH. In contrast, WW biochar exhibited no net shift in pH, consistent with wood-derived biochars' tendency to have lower ash content and thus weaker mineral-driven alkalinity. Although the 10% biochar addition was statistically distinct ($F = 19.65$, $p = 0.0011$), the magnitude of pH shifts was considered moderate.

Figure 4. Boxplots of Soil pH and Electrical Conductivity (EC) Following 10% Biochar Addition

Electrical conductivity (Figure 4b) increased substantially in soils amended with MSW and RT biochars, reaching 831–836 and 776–777 $\mu\text{mho/cm}$, respectively, compared within 641–642 $\mu\text{mho/cm}$ in the control ($F = 97.96$, $p < 0.0001$). These increases are consistent with the dissolution of soluble ash-derived ions such as K^+ , Ca^{2+} , and SO_4^{2-} , that readily leach from ash-rich biochars produced at intermediate to high temperatures [31]. Tire-derived chars, in particular, often contain ZnO , CaCO_3 , and salts associated with carbon black [32], which contribute to their intermediate EC elevation. By contrast, WW biochar produced minimal change in EC ($647 \mu\text{mho cm}^{-1}$), reflecting its low ash content and the limited solubility of minerals typical of lignocellulosic feedstocks. Importantly, despite measurable increases in the MSW and RT treatments, all EC values remained far below normal agronomic salinity thresholds of $<4,000 \mu\text{mho/cm}$ [33], indicating negligible salinity risk during the 45-day dry soil incubation.

Macronutrients

Nitrate-N concentrations remained low across all treatments, ranging from 0 to 1 ppm (Table 2). Although ANOVA detected statistically significant differences near zero ($F = 12.06$, $p = 0.0014$), the absolute values confirm that biochar additions did not increase plant-available nitrogen. This outcome reflects the tendency of high-temperature biochars to supply negligible mineral N and often promote microbial immobilization or adsorption-driven NO_3^- retention due to their high C:N ratios and reactive surfaces [34].

In contrast to nitrogen, phosphorus concentrations remained relatively stable across treatments (100–114 ppm), with slight increases in MSW and RT soils which were found as not statistically significant ($F = 0.90$, $p = 0.482$). Such small but measurable increases are consistent with the dissolution of P-bearing ash minerals, particularly under the near-neutral pH conditions of this early incubation, where phosphate remains relatively soluble and is not strongly precipitated [35]. The

lack of a substantial P increase, however, suggests that much of the P in these feedstocks may exist in less soluble Ca-bound mineral phases, limiting its release.

Table 2. Macronutrient Concentrations in Control and Biochar-Amended sSoils (mean ± SD).

Property	Control	MSW	RT	WW
	in ppm			
NO ₃ -N	1.08 ± 0.28 ^a	0.99 ± 0.32 ^a	0.13 ± 0.11 ^b	0.12 ± 0.16 ^b
P	106 ± 6 ^{ns}	111 ± 7 ^{ns}	114 ± 6 ^{ns}	100 ± 5 ^{ns}
K	922 ± 39 ^a	786 ± 53 ^b	853 ± 28 ^b	709 ± 23 ^c
Ca	1753 ± 36 ^b	1936 ± 38 ^a	1783 ± 32 ^b	1962 ± 35 ^a
S	49.3 ± 2.4 ^{ab}	45.6 ± 1.6 ^b	53.7 ± 2.4 ^a	47.2 ± 2.2 ^b

Note: Different letters within a row indicate statistically significant differences among treatments based on one-way fixed-effects ANOVA followed by Tukey's HSD test ($p < 0.05$). "ns" indicates no significant difference among treatments.

Potassium exhibited a distinct and unexpected trend. Instead of increasing, as is commonly observed for biochars rich in soluble K [36, 37], all treatments showed a reduction relative to the control, with MSW, RT, and WW treatments averaging at 770, 830, and 728 ppm compared to 931 ppm in the untreated soil. The results of the ANOVA ($F = 18.06$, $p = 0.0006$) indicate a significant treatment effect. This decline may result from K fixation within soil clay interlayers or microbial uptake stimulated by the introduction of carbon-rich materials. It may also reflect inherently low K content in the MSW and WW feedstocks prior to pyrolysis. RT biochar, which retained the highest K level among the treatments, aligns with literature describing moderate K enrichment in tire-derived chars [32]. Meanwhile, calcium increased consistently across all biochar-amended soils, rising by up to 212 ppm in the WW treatment and showing strong treatment effect ($F = 11.14$, $p = 0.00012$). This is consistent with dissolution of Ca-rich ash phases even under non-alkalizing conditions [28]. Magnesium, however, showed only minimal and inconsistent changes, reinforcing the notion that Mg solubility is more tightly regulated by pH and competitive adsorption processes [38]. Elevated Ca concentrations may contribute positively to soil aggregation and root development [39].

ANOVA results for the S measurements indicated modest variability across treatments and a small but statistically detectable effect ($F = 7.49$, $p = 0.012$). Extractable sulfur remained within a narrow range (46–53 ppm), with only a minor increase in the RT treatment. This aligns with reports that tire-derived biochars may retain trace sulfate and sulfur-containing functional groups [32]. Because S availability in soils is strongly controlled by organic matter mineralization and microbial processes [40], the modest treatment differences suggest limited oxidation of S-bearing functional groups or sulfur release during the incubation period.

Micronutrients and Trace Metals

Micronutrient availability (Table 3) declined markedly following biochar addition, with reductions of approximately 20–46%, and statistical analyses confirmed significant treatment effects for Cu ($F = 19.22$, $p = 0.0005$), Zn ($F = 17.61$, $p = 0.0007$), and Mn ($F = 19.38$, $p = 0.005$). Such depletion is consistent with established sorption and complexation behavior in high-temperature biochars, where abundant oxygen-containing functional groups, negative surface charge, and high surface area promote strong binding of transition-metal cations [41, 42]. The decrease in Zn levels in MSW and WW biochar amended soils may indicate Zn immobilization through sorption and dilution [43]. In contrast, RT biochar caused an increase in Zn which likely attributed to the high native Zn content of tire derived materials [32]. The decline in Cu shows a consistent pattern reflecting strong Cu sorption by functional groups present on biochar surfaces. The RT biochar reduced Cu despite increasing Zn because tire-derived chars contain abundant mineral phases that effectively bind Cu [44]. The simultaneous increases in Ca and decreases in Cu and Mn suggest that precipitation of micronutrient carbonates or phosphates may also be occurring, as previously reported in neutral to slightly acidic soils amended with mineral-rich biochars [41]. Both MSW and WW biochars acted primarily as metal immobilizers, reducing Zn and Cu, while RT biochar increased Zn due to feedstock derived metal inputs. These results highlight the importance of feedstock selection in managing trace metal behavior in biochar amended soils.

Table 3. Micronutrient Concentrations in Control and Biochar-Amended Soils (mean ± SD).

Property	Control	10%MSW	10%RT	10%WW
	in ppm			
Copper	2.94 ± 0.3 ^a	1.88 ± 0.09 ^{ab}	1.62 ± 0.15 ^b	2.02 ± 0.12 ^b
Zinc	5.87 ± 0.82 ^b	5.46 ± 0.85 ^b	8.93 ± 0.35 ^a	4.73 ± 0.22 ^b
Manganese	24.53 ± 0.97 ^a	19.67 ± 0.82 ^b	19.73 ± 01.09 ^b	17.53 ± 0.9 ^c

Note: Different letters within a row indicate statistically significant differences among treatments based on one-way fixed-effects ANOVA followed by Tukey’s HSD test ($p < 0.05$). “ns” indicates no significant difference among treatments.

Table 4 summarizes the concentrations of Ni, Cr, Pb, Cd, and As in the MSW, RT, and WW biochars. These metals represent some of the key indicators of potential toxicity and environmental risk. Furthermore, comparison with the international biochar regulatory values [24, 45] provides a basis for assessing the suitability of each biochar for soil application.

Table 4. Trace Metal Concentrations (mean ± SD) in MSW, RT, and WW Biochars Compared with Allowable Limits in the IBI and WBC-Agro Standards

Biochar	Ni	Cr	Pb	Cd	As
	in ppm				
MSW	70.1 ± 7.3 ^f	40.2 ± 3.8	4.31 ± 0.22	0.44 ± 0.03	0.15 ± 0.01
RT	43 ± 2.6	21.4 ± 1.3	14.1 ± 1.7	0.77 ± 0.05	0.36 ± 0.03
WW	24.3 ± 3.0	3.9 ± 0.3	22.8 ± 2.1	0.96 ± 0.09	0.56 ± 0.04
IBI Standards	47-420	93-1200	121-300	1.4-39	13-100
WBC-Agro	100	200	300	5	20

Nickel was most abundant in MSW biochar at 70.1 ppm. Nickel is known to impair root development, reduce nutrient uptake, and accumulate in plant tissues, particularly within Brassica species [46]. Nickel concentrations in the RT and WW biochar were lower at 43 ppm and 24.3 ppm, respectively, and remain compliant with regulatory standards. Chromium concentrations were highest in MSW biochar at 40.2 ppm, followed by RT biochar at 21.4 ppm, with WW biochar containing only 3.9 ppm. Although all values fall below the IBI limit of 93 ppm, Cr requires careful interpretation due to differences in toxicity between the trivalent and hexavalent forms [47]. The MSW value is consistent with Cr-containing pigments and metal fragments in municipal waste, and further analysis of Cr mobility may be warranted.

Lead concentrations were low across all samples and measured 22.8 ppm in WW biochar, 14.1 ppm in RT biochar, and 4.31 ppm in MSW biochar. These values are below the IBI threshold and reflect contributions from painted wood, rubber additives, and small electronic components [48-50]. Lead binds strongly to soil particles, which limits immediate mobility but increases the potential for long term accumulation [51]. Cadmium concentrations ranged from 0.44 to 0.958 ppm and were below the IBI limit. Cadmium is highly mobile in soil and readily taken up by leafy vegetables and root crops, which means that even low inputs can contribute to gradual buildup in agricultural soils [52]. Arsenic concentrations were below 1 ppm and show minimal immediate concern.

The measured levels of Cr, Pb, Cd, and As, in this study present manageable risks when these specific biochars are applied at moderate rates and under controlled soil conditions. However, it is important to interpret these observations as early-stage responses that occurred under dry incubation conditions, where limited dissolution and restricted microbial activity may have reduced the mobility of metal species.

Soil Benefits, Environmental Risk, and Circularity

The soil responses observed in this study suggest that waste-derived biochars can influence several aspects of soil chemistry in ways that may be beneficial under certain conditions. Increases in exchangeable Ca following MSW and WW additions point to modest improvements in the soil environment that may influence conditions associated with aggregation and root growth potential. The rise in EC in MSW- and RT-amended soils is consistent with limited ash dissolution and remained well below salinity thresholds. The biochars therefore released soluble ions at levels

unlikely to cause salt-related stress during the incubation. Indicators of carbon stability were also apparent in the MSW and RT biochars, suggesting potential for longer-term carbon persistence once added to soil.

Micronutrient patterns provide additional context for these observations. Reductions in Cu and Mn across most treatments reflect their strong affinity for biochar surfaces. This may moderate soluble forms of these micronutrients, although it could also reduce their short-term availability. Zinc behavior differed among feedstocks. MSW and WW tended to lower soil Zn, whereas RT increased it. These contrasting responses highlight the influence of feedstock composition in shaping micronutrient outcomes [44].

The trace metal results indicate relatively low concentrations of Ni, Cr, Pb, Cd, and As in all three biochars. These values fall within regulatory limits, although their longer-term mobility remains uncertain. The dry incubation used here likely limited dissolution and microbial transformation. Field conditions with greater moisture variability or stronger biogeochemical activity may alter metal behavior over time [53]. Continued monitoring is therefore advisable when applying waste-derived biochars to soils used for crop production or long-term land management.

When these responses are considered together, they suggest that MSW and RT biochars function mainly as soil conditioners rather than as direct nutrient sources. They can influence pH, EC, and the retention or release of nutrients and trace metals, while also introducing carbon that may persist for extended periods. These combined effects informed the development of a circular waste-to-biochar framework that illustrates their potential role in the bioeconomy (Figure 5). Converting MSW and RT into carbon-rich materials creates a pathway in which waste management, soil improvement, and climate mitigation can operate together. The stability of the carbon in these materials adds further value by redirecting carbon away from landfills, open dumping, or incineration and into more persistent soil pools. This shift may also support opportunities for verified carbon crediting, depending on applicable standards.

Figure 5. Circular Waste-to-Biochar Pathway Illustrating Biochar Production, Field Application, Soil Benefits, Long-Term Carbon Storage Potential, and Potential Environmental Safeguards and Monitoring Practices Identified in This Study

This circular pathway depends not only on the intrinsic stability of the biochar but also on safeguards that ensure its safe and effective use. Moderating application rates, blending high-metal feedstocks with cleaner materials, and monitoring soil and plant responses are practical measures that support responsible deployment. Overall, the findings of this study show how circular-economy principles can help transform persistent wastes into environmental assets with potential agronomic and climate benefits.

CONCLUSION

This screening-level study demonstrates that waste-derived biochars produced from municipal solid waste and rubber tires at 500 °C exhibit high carbon stability alongside measurable short-term soil chemical responses. MSW- and RT-derived biochars contained 85-88% carbon and showed low atomic ratios ($H/C \leq 0.40$; $O/C \leq 0.08$), high fixed carbon contents (72-78%), and carbon retention of approximately 52-53% of the original feedstock carbon during pyrolysis. These characteristics place MSW and RT biochars within published stability classes associated with highly aromatic carbon and long modeled persistence in soil environments. When combined with stability-based permanence factors, carbon sequestration efficiencies of approximately 38-39% were estimated for MSW and RT biochars, compared with about 22% for wood-derived biochar, indicating greater relative carbon retention potential under long-term soil application scenarios. Together, these results support the classification of MSW- and RT-derived biochars as chemically recalcitrant, carbon-rich materials suitable for further evaluation as soil-applied carbon storage media.

Short-term soil incubation revealed moderate changes in soil chemistry that primarily reflected limited ash dissolution. The EC increased modestly but remained below salinity thresholds, and exchangeable calcium increased consistently across treatments. Soil pH declined slightly following MSW and RT biochar addition, while changes in nutrient availability and micronutrient concentrations were generally small. These responses suggest that early soil-biochar interactions are chemically moderate and do not induce acute salinity stress or micronutrient imbalance under controlled conditions. However, several considerations remain for field application. Slight soil acidification may influence metal mobility under variable moisture regimes, and the elevated metal content of some waste-derived feedstocks warrants continued evaluation. Although trace metals exhibited limited mobility during the short-term incubation, their behavior under dynamic field-relevant conditions remains uncertain. Future research should prioritize longer-term incubations and field studies using realistic application rates and seasonal moisture conditions. Risk-based management strategies, including appropriate site selection and routine monitoring of soil pH and metal concentrations, will be essential. With appropriate safeguards, MSW- and RT-derived biochars represent a potential pathway for converting persistent wastes into long-lived soil-applied carbon materials within circular waste management systems.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This research was made possible through the support of the eAI Institute, Magnolia, TX, USA. All pre-processed materials were graciously provided by them, and the associated data remain proprietary to the Institute.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

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